

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15249217

Effects Of Cow And Rabbit Urine Application On The Growth And Quality Of Fluted Pumpkin (*Telfairia occidentalis* Hook F) In Southern Nigeria

¹Nmor, E. I; ²Alyelari, O. P, ³Agele, S.O, ⁴Adebayo, R.A, ⁵Ogboi, E. and ⁶Ewododhe A. A.C

^{1,5,6}Department of Agronomy,
Southern Delta University, Ozoro, Delta State, Nigeria

^{2,3,4}Department of Crop, Soil and Pest management,
Federal University of Technology, Akure, Nigeria

*Corresponding Author Email: abelakpotu@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This research was carried out in the research and Teaching Farm of Faculty of Agriculture in Southern Delta University (SDU), Ozoro in Isoko North local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. The continuous cultivation of land due to sharp increase in population, thus reduce the available farm land for agricultural activities motivated the farmers to use inorganic fertilizers to boost production. The need to determine the effect of rabbit and cow urine on growth and quality of fluted pumpkin was prompted by setback like soil degradation, scarcity, water pollution and unsustainable nature of this compound. The design was laid out in Randomized Complete Block Design with three replications. The strength of the study is a measured of the leaf area, vine length, leaf area index, fresh leaf weight and the number of leaves. Data collected were subjected to analysis of variances (ANOVA), and means were separated using Turkey's HSD. The result revealed that pumpkin grown under cow urine had better number of leaves and vine length while those pumpkin grown under rabbit urine performed better in terms of leaf area, leaf area index. It is therefore recommended that farmers in the study area should use cow urine for the cultivation of pumpkin since emphasis were on the leaves and vine than other parameters.

Keywords: Cow, Rabbit, Urine, Pumpkin, Growth.

INTRODUCTION

Fluted pumpkin (*Telfairia occidentalis*), a member of the Cucurbitaceae family, is predominantly cultivated in the eastern regions of Nigeria due to its significant nutritional, medicinal, and industrial benefits. Its cultivation has expanded throughout Nigeria owing to increased awareness of its value. The leaves are commonly harvested for use in soups and porridge, while the flour derived from the seeds serves as an ingredient in bread and various snacks. Also, the seeds produce oil which can be used in the making of soap (Esiaba, 1992). As consumer awareness of fluted pumpkin's advantages has grown (Kumar et al., 2014), so has the demand for the crop. A major determinant of fluted pumpkin yield is the nutritional quality of the soil (Ochilo et al., 2019), while pests and diseases serve as primary threats to yield quality (Sumaili et al., 2021). The continuous use of inorganic fertilizers and synthetic pesticides presents drawbacks, such as soil degradation, nutrient imbalance, high costs, and environmental concerns (Morals et al., 2005). Thus, organic fertilizers and bio-pesticides are proposed as sustainable alternatives to enhance the yield and quality of fluted pumpkin (Desta et al., 2022).

Rabbit urine functioning as both a bio-pesticide and bio-fertilizer, still emerges as a versatile option. Nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium are important bio-fertilizer from these animals' urine (Yogeeshappa and Srinivasamurthy, 2017). Soil acidity caused by chemical fertilizers could easily be counteracted by the alkaline nature of rabbit urine with a pH value of 8.5. Furthermore, soil health promoted by rabbit urine enhances soil organic matter, microbial activity and soil aeration (Said *et al.*, 2018).

While cow urine concentrate has also been discovered to be a biopesticide and biofertilizer (Dharma *et al.*, 2005), it is crucial to compare its effectiveness to that of rabbit urine. Cow urine supports the growth of crops, like maize, lettuce, rice and mustard can be promoted by cow urine (Devakumar *et al.*, 2014; Pradhan *et al.*, 2016; Oliveira *et al.*, 2019; Qibtiyah *et al.*, 2015), with studies indicating that a 5-10% concentration can significantly enhance plant growth attributes (Tamaraker *et al.*, 2016). For instance, cow urine applications led to substantial yield improvements across crops such as maize and rice (Dvakumar *et al.*, 2014; Sharma *et al.*, 2016). Other studies highlight the beneficial effects of cow urine on the growth of crops like cauliflower, amaranthus, and pumpkin, indicating greater biomass production and yield when used in conjunction with biochar (Schmidt *et al.*, 2015).

This study aims to investigate the potential of livestock urine in promoting the growth and quality of fluted pumpkin. The specific objectives include assessing the impacts of cow urine on fluted pumpkin performance, evaluating the effects of rabbit urine, comparing the efficacy of both types of urine, and identifying the most effective urine type for fluted pumpkin cultivation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Site

This research was carried out in Agronomy Research and Teaching Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture in Southern Delta University, (SDU), Ozoro in Isoko North Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. Isoko North is located between Latitudes; 6° 30'11"N and 6° 45'11"N of the Equator and Longitude: 5° 45'11"E and 6° 13'11"E of the Greenwich Meridian. Ozoro has annual rainfall of 2500 – 3000 mm and mean annual temperature ranging from 28 – 30°C, below 50 meters above the sea level in a tropical rainfall zone of Nigeria.

Urine and Seed Collection: Cow urine was collected from cattle ranch while rabbit urine was collected from the hutches of Delta State University of Science and Technology, Research and Teaching Farm of Faculty of Agriculture. The urines were cured for 14 days to reduce the acidity of the urine

Soil Sample and Urine Analysis: Soil samples collected randomly from the experimental site were taken to the laboratory for physical chemical analysis. Moreso, the urines were also analyzed for their chemical composition.

Experimental Design: The design was laid out in Randomized Complete Block Design which was replicated three times.

Data Collection

Data were collected at interval of two weeks

The growth parameters that were determined were as follows:

- Number of Leave: This is done by counting.
- Plant height was done with measuring tape.
- Leaf Area: The average leaf areas in cm² was calculated as:

$$\text{Leaf Area} = \frac{(L1 \times W1) + (L2 \times W2) + (L3 \times W3)}{3}$$

Where: L1 – 3 = length for the three readings

W1 – 3 = width for the three readings

(Silva *et al.*, 1998)

Then the entire leaf area for the plant = single leaf area x number of leaves per plot.

4. Leaf Area Index = $\frac{\text{Leaf Area}}{\text{Spacing}} = \frac{L.A}{.5 \times .6}$ or $\frac{L.A}{50 \times 60 \text{ cm}}$

5. Fresh weight of leaf – This was determined using the sensitive weighing scale (grams)

6. Nutritive or proximate yield was done after harvest, the leaves were taken to the lab for analysis for nutritive content of each of the treatment (rabbit and cow urine).

Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance and means were separated using Tukey's HSD at 5% level of probability.

4.0 RESULTS

Table 4.1 provides an overview of the chemical features of the soils tried from the study area. The findings indicated that the soil pH was measured at 4.33 (12 H₂O). The organic carbon content was set up to be 0.47, while the organic matter position was 1.32. Specifically, nitrogen was recorded at 0.10 mg/ kg, phosphorus at 4.67 mg/ kg, and potassium (K) at 0.41 mg/ kg. Also, the attention of sodium (Na), magnesium (Mg), calcium (Ca), and iron(Fe) were 0.40 mg/ kg, 1.0 mg/kg, 2.10 mg/ kg, and 0.19 mg/ kg, independently. The situations of lead (Pb) were measured at 0.03 ppm, copper at 0.24ppm and zinc (Zn) at 0.24 ppm.

Table 4.1: Chemical properties of the soil of the study area.

Chemical Properties	Values
pH 1.2 (H ₂ O)	4.33
Oc (5%)	0.77
Om (%)	1.32
N (mg/kg)	0.10
P (mg/kg)	4.67
K (mg/kg)	0.41
Na (mg/kg)	0.40
Cm (mg/kg)	2.10
Mg (mg/kg)	1.00
Fe (ppm)	0.19
Zn (ppm)	0.24
Cu (ppm)	0.24
Pb (ppm)	0.03

4.1.2 Livestock Urine Composition

Table 4.2 presents the analysis results of two sources of livestock urine (cow and rabbit urine). The results showed that the nitrogen content ranged from 0.33 to 0.37, with the highest value of 0.37 recorded in cow urine, while rabbit urine had a value of 0.33. The findings further indicate that cow urine contained the highest levels of phosphorus (7.53), potassium (11.31), calcium (5.56), and magnesium (1.62), compared to rabbit urine, which recorded values of 6.32 for phosphorus, 6.14 for potassium, 2.68 for calcium, and 1.42 for magnesium. Cow urine also had the highest concentration of iron at 8.16 ppm, while rabbit urine had only 0.10 ppm. For manganese and lead, both types of urine had low levels of zinc, compared to 0.25 ppm for rabbit urine. Additionally, cow urine had the highest copper content at 0.20 ppm, whereas rabbit urine contained 0.07 ppm.

Table 4.2: The result of the analysis of three sources of livestock urine (cow and rabbit)

	%	mg/100g					ppm				
	N	P	K	Ca	Mg	Fe	Mn	Pb	Zn	Cu	
Cow	0.37	7.53	11.31	5.56	1.62	0.16	0.10	0.01	0.23	0.20	
Rabbit	0.33	6.32	6.14	2.68	1.42	0.10	0.10	0.01	0.25	0.07	

Table 4.3 reveals the effect of animal urine on the number of leaves of fluted pumpkin. The results show that pumpkins grown with cow urine had the most numerous number of leaves throughout the experimental period. Considering 5% level of significance, at weeks 6 and 8, there were significant

differences among the treatments; still, at weeks 10 and 12, there were no significant differences among the treatments.

Table 4.3: Effects of Livestock urine application on the number of *Telfairia occidentalis*

Livestock Urine: Week After Treatment Application

Livestock Urine	6	8	10	12
Rabbit	16.58b	22.5bc	29.6922.59b	35.726
Cow	18.53a	28.14b	33.6ab	34.97b

Table 4.4 presents the effects of livestock urine application on the vine length of *Telfairia occidentalis*. The result indicated that cow urine results in the longest vine length throughout the duration of the experiment. However, there was no significant difference among the treatments, except at week 12, where a significant difference was observed among the treatments.

Table 4.4: Effect of livestock urine application on the length of *Telfairia occidentalis*

Livestock Urine	6	8	10	12
Cow	154.81a	160.75a	170.039	225.17b
Rabbit	140.28a	157.14a	165.50a	196.5c

Table (4.5) shows the effects of livestock urine on the yield parameters of *Telfairia occidentalis*. The result revealed that rabbit urine had the highest leaf area and leaf area index while the highest fresh was recorded in cow urine treatments.

There was no significant difference among the treatments.

Table 4.5: Effect of livestock urine on yield parameters of *Telfairia Occidentalis*

Livestock Urine	Leaf area	Leaf area index	Fresh weight
Cow	922.53c	3.08a	0.73a
Rabbit	2679.96b	8.93b	0.59a

Table 4.6 reveals the effects of livestock urine on the proximate composition of *Telfairia occidentalis*. The results showed that pumpkins grown with rabbit urine had the highest moisture content of 75.81, compared to 75.67 recorded for the cow urine treatment. There was a significant difference among the treatments. Rabbit urine also recorded the highest ash content, while the pumpkins grown under cow urine had the lowest ash content of 2.14. Significant differences were observed among the treatments in this regard as well. The results further indicate that pumpkins grown with cow urine recorded the highest percentage of fat, at 3.54, compared to 3.41 for those grown under rabbit urine with treatment in this category showing significant differences. There were also significant differences among the treatments in this category. Additionally, pumpkins grown with cow urine had the highest percentages of crude fiber and protein, with significant differences noted among the treatments. The highest percentage of carbohydrates was found in pumpkins grown with rabbit urine, and significant differences were observed among all treatments at the 5% level of significance.

Table 4.6: Effects of livestock urine on proximate composition of *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves.

Livestock urine	Moisture content	Ash	Fat	Crude	protein	Carbohydrate
Cow	75.67b	2.14b	3.54a	7.49a	9.56b	1.60b
Rabbit	75.81a	2.29a	3.41c	7.33c	9.44c	1.74a

DISCUSSION

The results from the findings show that livestock urine had positively influenced the growth and quality of fluted pumpkin. The results which revealed that pumpkins grown with cow urine performed better in terms of the number of leaves and vine length, and also at 5% level of probability showed that there were

significant differences among the treatments, agrees with the findings of Devakumar et al. (2014), Pradhan et al. (2016), Oliveira et al. (2009), and Qibttayah et al. 2015. This finding was further strengthened by WHO 2015, discovery that showed that using cow urine enhanced the growth of various crop types. Cow urine application significantly improved vegetative parameters such as plant height, number of leaves, and length and width of the plants (Tarmaraker et al., 2016). These results align with the findings of other authors like Patil et al. (2012), who reported that chickpeas grown with cow urine application recorded higher plant height, higher number of leaves, higher index, more pods per plant, and higher grain quality compared to the control. Kumar et al. (2014) reported that bush jasmine grown with cow urine performed better in terms of productivity. Cow urine application enhances soil nutrient status and the yield of agronomic growth parameters of maize (Nwite, 2015). The findings align with Abraham and Lal (2004), who recorded that cow urine application plus PSB resulted in higher grain and biological yield than PSB plus *Azospirillum*. Moreover, other authors observed that the application of cow urine increased seed yield (Pradhan et al. 2016.). The highest biomass was recorded in amaranth grown under cow urine application compared to the control (Adeoluwa et al., 2009). Pumpkins treated with cow urine and biomass application yielded more compared to those with only biochar application (Schmidt et al., 2015). According to Damodhar et al. (2010), the use of cow urine led to the greatest weight of fruits, the highest number of fruits, and increased overall fruit yield when compared to the control group. The experiment revealed that pumpkins grown under rabbit urine application recorded the highest leaf area, leaf area index, and fresh leaf weight. This result corroborates the findings of Muh Aiwi et al. (2021), who reported that shallots treated with Bokashi and rabbit urine had the best bulb number compared to the control. Barker and Pibean (2007) reported that cucumbers grown under rabbit urine application performed better. Tomatoes treated with rabbit urine and NPK fertilizer had the highest yield and yield parameters according to Ndabo and Abubarka (2020). Atia et al. (2005) reported that melons grown under rabbit urine application had the highest number of leaves and the highest plant height. Ndabo and Abubakar (2020) stated that tomatoes grown under livestock urine treatment had better numbers of branches, leaf area, and leaf area index. Akanbi et al. (2010) reported that livestock urine improved cellular activities, which enhanced cell multiplication and the enlargement of fluted pumpkin.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Although both rabbit and cow urine had significant influenced on the growth and yield parameters of pumpkin in terms of number of leaves, plant height, leaves area, index and fresh leaf. However, cow urine performed better in terms of number of leaves, plant, height and proximate composition. It is therefore recommended that cow urine should be used for the cultivation of pumpkin in the study area and its environ to boost the income of the farmers. Moreso research should be carried out on other livestock urine such as goat, sheep and pig.

REFERENCES

- Adeoluwa, O. O. & Cofie, O. (2012). *Urine as an alternative fertilizer in Agriculture; Effect in Amaranthes (Amaranthus caudatus) production Renewable Agriculture and food System* 8:1. doi 10:1017/51742170- 511000512
- Akanbi, W. B., Togun, A O., Adodiran, J. A. Ilupoju, (2010). Growth dry matter and fruit yield component of okra undry organic and inorganic source of nutrients American. *Journal of sustainable Agriculture*. 4(1): 1 – 13.
- Atia, A.; Haugen-Kozyra, K. & Amrani, M. (2005). *Ammonia and hydrogen sulfide emissions from livestock production. Urine research findings and technologies: From Science to Social Issue* (online) Alberta Agriculture, Food and Rural Development. Pp. 47.
- Damodhar, V. P. & Shide, V.V. (2010): Effect of Cow Urine Sprays on yield and quality of mango (*mangifera indica*) cv. Alphonso. *The Asian J. Horticulture*, 5(2): 307-308.
- Devakumar, N., Shubha, S., Rao, G. G. E. and Imrankhan. (2014): *Studies on Soil Fertility, Cow Urine and Panchagavya Levels of Growth and Yield of Maize*.

- Esiaba, R.O (1982). *Propagation and fluted pumpkin (Telfairia occidentalis)*, proceeding of the 5th annual conference of Horticultural society of Nigeria, zaira, pp 79-90.
- Gadelha R.S.S., Celestino, R.C.A., Shimoya, A. 2003. Efeito da utilização de urina de vaca na produção da alface. *Pesquisa Agropecuária & Desenvolvimento Sustentável*, 1: 179-182
- Indabo, S.S. & Abubakar, A. A. (2020): Effect of Rabbit Urine Application Rates as a Bioterilizer on Agro-Morphological Traits of UC82B Tomato (*Lycopersicon Esculentum mill*) Variety in Zaria, Nigeria. *Dutse Journal of Pure and applied science*, vol 6 (2):344-352
- Jandaik, S., Thakur, P. & Kumari V., (2015): Efficacy of Cow Urine as Plant growth enhancer and antifungal agent. *Ach. Agri*. Volume 2015, Artimle ID620368, 7 pages.
- Kumar, M. (2014): Influence of seed priming with urine, phosphorus and zinc on maize (*zea mays L.*) Yield in an acidic soil of Northeast India. *Indian J. Hill Farming*, 27(1): 132-137.
- Lekamoi, U., Kusolwa, P., Mbega, E. R. (2022): Effect of Tephrosia vogeliiformulation with rabbit urine on insect pests and yield of sesame in Singida, Tanzania. *Journal of Biodiversity and Environmental Sciences*. 20: 1–13.
- Muh, A. I. W., Husen, Sugiyarto Sugiyarto & Esna D. N. (2021). The effect of bokashi and rabbit urine addition on the tuber of shallots (*Allium ascalonicum L.*) advances in *Biological Science Research*. Vol. 22 p. 102 – 105.
- Mutai, P. A. (2020): The potential use of rabbit urine as a bio-fertilizer foliar feed in crop production. *Africa Environmental Review Journal*. 4: 137–144.
- Nwite J. N. (2015). Effect of different urine sources on soil chemical properties and maize in Abakaliki, south eastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Agricultural Research*. Vol(3): 31 – 36.
- Ochilo, Willis.N., Nyamasyo, Gideon.N., Kilalo, D., Otieno, W., Otipa, M., Chege, F., Karanja, T., Lingerera, & Eunice.K. (2019): Characteristics and production constraints of smallholder tomato production in Kenya. *Scientific African*.
- Pathak, R.K. & Ram, R.A. 2013. Bioenhancers: A potential tool to improve soil fertility, plant health in organic production of horticultural crops. *Progressive Horticulture*, 45(2): 237- 254.
- Patil, S. V., Hallkatti, S. I., Hiremath, S. M. Babalad, H. B. Sreenivasa, M. N. Habsur, N. S. & Somanagouda, G. (2012). Effect of livestock urine on growth and yield of chickpea (*cicer arietinum L.*) in vertisols. *Karnataka Journal of Agricultural Science*. 25(3): 326 – 331.
- Pradhan S., Bohra, J. S. Bahadur, S., Rajani and Ram, L. (2016): *J. Pure and Appl. Microbiol*, 10(2). P. 1637.
- Said, M. C Asriany, A M., Sirajuddin, S. B. Abustam, L. E. Rasyid, B. & AL-Tawaha, A.R. 11 (2018) Evaluation of Quality of Liquid Organic Fertilizer From Rabbit urine Waste Fermented using Local Micro-organism as Decomposer. *Iragui Journal Agricultural Science*, 49(6):990-1003
- Schmidt, H. P., Pandit, B. H., Martinsen, V., Cornelissen, G., Conte, P. & Kammann, C. I. (2015): *Fourfold increase in pumpkin yield on response of low dosage root zone application of urine-enhanced bio-char to a fertile tropical soil*. *Agri*. 5:723-741.
- Sharma, Shah, S. C., Adhikari, K. R., Shah, P., & Shrestha, J., (2016). Effect of Cattle Urine and FYM on Yield of Broccoli and Soil Properties. *J. Agric. Search*, 3(3): 157-160.
- Sri Utami Lestari & Andi Andrian (2017): Effect of Urine Cow Dosage on Growth and Production of Sorghum Plant (*Sorghum Bicolor L.*) on Peat Land. 10P Conf. Ser. *Earth Environ. Sci*. 97 012052.
- Sumaili, J. M., Saidi, M., Kamau,A.W. (2021): Controlling greenhouse whitefly with *Erectomocerus eremicus*Rose & Zolnerowich and crude plant extracts of garlic and chilli improves yield of tomato. *NASS Journal of Agricultural Sciences*.
- Sunadra, I. K., Mudra, N. L. K. S., Wirajaya, A.Agung.Ngurah.M., Yuliantini, M.S., Kartini, L., Udayana, I. G. B., & Mahardika, I. B. K. (2019): Response to growth and yield melon plant (*Cucumis MeloL.*) in the giving of rabbit urine and KNO₃. *Sustainable Environment Agricultural Science*.

- Tamarkar, S. K. (2016). *Effect of plant growth regulators, vermicast and cow urine on vegetative growth, flowering, corm production and vase life of gladiolus var. Candyman*. Ph. D. thesis, Department of horticulture, college of agriculture, Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Raipur (Chhattisgarh).
- Umekwe, P. N.; Eneruvie, B. E. & Okpani, E. M. (2020). Effect of livestock urine on the growth and yield of fluted pumpkin (*Telfaria occidentalis* Hook F.) in Unwana. *World Journal of Innovation Research*. 153 N: 2454 – 8236 Vol 9, Issue 5.
- Yogeeshappa, H. & Srinivasamurthy, C.A. (2017) Effect of Human Urine and Cattle Urine on Growth and yield of Tomato (*Solanum Lycopersicum*) in Red, Lateritic and Black Soils of karnata India. *International Journal of current Microbiology and Applied Science* ISSN SN: 2319-7706 volume 1597-16051 6 number 120 PP